

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN THE TRANSLATION OF REALISTICS

G'ulomova Bibi Muxlisa Maxmudjonovna

Student of the Faculty of English Philology,
Teaching Methodology and Translation Studies
Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages.
gulomovamukxlisa@gmail.com

Abstract. *The article describes the unity of reality, different images of reality, and the role of reality in the illumination of cultural characteristics. Methods of translating reality, in particular, translation, are discussed. The difference between the real and the terms is revealed. Real units specific to the Uzbek language, translated by the translation method, were analyzed. Their semantic features are explained. It is emphasized that the semantics of real units is related to the worldview, lifestyle, and cultural relations of the people. It is shown through examples that the translation method of translating reality is used as the wealth of the created language of the artistic text, it is assimilated into the translated language, it increases the wealth of the vocabulary, and it reflects the wealth of the national vocabulary. color It is noted that expanding the scope of research on the semantics of real units and the translation of reals is of practical importance in studying the internal development features of a particular language and in illuminating intercultural relations.*

Methods of translation of real units are aimed at clarifying the problem of reproducing the semantics of lexemes in another language. Reconstruction of the

semantics of real units is carried out in different ways. Translation, which is one of these methods, allows to reflect the national color in the translation. But the truth is that it is not always possible to clarify the semantics of a unit. Additional explanations are needed to clarify the semantics of the unit of reality and to reflect its pragmatic meanings in the original language. Realities, as a symbol of the national-cultural environment, and as an expression of values, give a special spirit to the artistic text. Translating realities requires the translator to know cultural symbols in addition to language knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to linguistic competence in the formation of translator specialists. Linguistic competence is formed based on a perfect mastery of the mother tongue. Mastering the mother tongue should be built not only on the use of communication and emotional expressive functions but also based on understanding cultural attitudes and values. A specialist who knows his mother tongue will have the opportunity to learn another language in a cultural environment. Special attention should be paid to this issue when training translators. Realism plays an important role in the study of interlinguistic and intercultural differences in translation studies, comparative linguistics, cultural studies, and ethnolinguistics. Reality serves to illuminate the level of cultural relations and reflects the concepts of people's lifestyles. Realities are concepts formed at the later stages of the development of an individual society and correspond to the periods when differences between cultures arose. The main feature that distinguishes reality from other similar concepts is that they have the meaning of object-thing. The original meaning of reality is the concept of objects that reflect the specific characteristics of cultures. The etymology of the word "realia" is equivalent to the Latin concept of "material". Realities can be evaluated as signs of material culture. In linguistics and translation studies, words and phrases representing objects are called reality in a broad sense.

In classical grammar, reality is interpreted as external linguistics that studies

the state system, national history, culture and language, and communication of the speakers of a given country, as well as various other factors and cultural objects. D.E. Rosenthal, M.A. Telenkova defined reality as "existing cultural objects that serve as the basis for the nominative meaning of the word." According to L.N. Sobolev, non-equivalent household and specific national words and phrases, as well as units related to the national way of life that does not exist in other languages, are considered "reality" because these things and events occur in other countries. Will not be available. A.V. Fedorov understands "truth" as "words denoting social life and material lifestyle", representing only local phenomena and having no equal in the life and understanding of other peoples. According to T. I. Cheremisina, "realia-words are words defined in the local sense and serve to define customs and household items characteristic of a certain people." G.D. Tomakhin defines it as follows: "Reality - objects of material culture, historical evidence, state institutions, heroes of national and folklore, mythical creatures, etc. belong only to certain nations and peoples." this name"

We noted that realism is often observed in artistic texts. Therefore, distortion of reality in the translation of artistic texts is a special problem of translation studies. Realism translation requires a specialist to have a certain level of knowledge and skills regarding the features of the language in which the artistic work was created, and the culture, lifestyle, customs, and traditions of its owners. The correct translation of the facts ensures that the units in the literary text are projected into the reader's mind appropriately. In all languages, there are several ways to convey the reality of the foreign language to the mind of the reader. Y. Maslov distinguishes the method of "material appropriation" or appropriation in a private sense. In such cases, not only the lexical meaning of foreign language units but also their close meanings of one or another level - the material index - are mastered: the most common types of "material acquisition" are translation and transcription. Transcription and transliteration are often used to reproduce famous

names, names of public enterprises, educational institutions, etc. Translation is a French word that means "to translate." this is enough (for example, Gamzatov - Hamzatov). In other words, translation is the clear transmission of words in graphic forms. As a result of the cultural-educational, economic, and political relations between the countries, the meanings, and functions of many words expressing the concepts of the life of certain peoples become familiar to the representatives of many peoples, including the owners of the translation language, that is why. translators interpret such words in their language using translation without looking for alternative linguistic means.

The main reason for using the translation method is that there is no alternative in the translated language for the national language tools used in the original version. Translation is one of the most effective ways to interpret specific words that reflect the concepts of certain people's lifestyles. Although there are meaningful units in the translated language that are somewhat closer to the meanings of the original linguistic means, differences are noticeable in the patterns of lexical units. In this case, the broadcast method serves to eliminate the problem. It is the student's opinion about a certain environment that is transmitted through the transmission of words that mean many concepts, such as units of money and distance, household goods, clothes, food, and drinks, typical of the people who arrived. and conditions. This will ensure that it is visible in front of you.

CONCLUSION. From the above, it can be concluded that the translator effectively used both the translation method and translation and interpretation methods in translating the Uzbek national reality into Russian and completed his work. In the process of language learning, real units are also of practical importance. The science of linguistics, which examines the issues of language education based on the requirements of the times, pays attention to the acquisition of cultural signs. Realism is also important in elucidating the meaning of the vocabulary, phraseological layer, figurative expression, and similes of the

language. Translating reality helps express reality clearly in language culture. The translation method also has its limitations. The use of such a method leads to the emergence of unstudied and incomprehensible words in the translation. Nevertheless, it ensures the widespread diffusion of concepts specific to a particular national culture to other cultures. In addition to providing information about a specific object, the real units in the artistic text also represent national-cultural symbols, cognitive symbols, and pragmatic meanings reflected in the linguistic expression of this object. The study of real units is important in analyzing the semantic development of lexemes. The units of reality represent the concepts of the way of life of certain people, and over time their semantic content shows cultural attitudes, cognitive signs, values , and values.

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